

1 **European Negotiation Conference 2025**

2 **ENC Interview Questions – John Hemery responses**

3 **1. Role & Vantage Point**

4 *Briefly tell us what you do and how negotiation features in your everyday*
5 *work.*

6 After an earlier career as a history teacher and professor of international
7 relations, in 1993 I founded the Centre for Political and Diplomatic
8 Studies (CPDS), building on the programmes of diplomatic training for the
9 new foreign ministries of Central and Eastern Europe and the former Soviet
10 Union I had conducted at the University of Leeds (1991-93), funded by the
11 UK Foreign and Commonwealth Office.

12 Since then CPDS has offered training in the soft skills of diplomacy
13 (policy-making, negotiating, influencing, communicating) to some 50,000
14 people, new entrants to ambassadors and ministers from 108 countries, six
15 international institutions and a number of corporate entities.

16 At the heart of almost all our programmes are negotiation skills. Over the
17 years I have had the privilege of learning the art and science of
18 negotiation from our course directors, all distinguished former senior
19 diplomats, with an extraordinary range of knowledge and experience. I
20 have

21 learnt, too, from others in our field, first among them Paul Meerts (who
22 coined the telling term ‘egotiation’), whose scholarship, imagination and
23 sense of humour continue to inspire an army of devoted followers.

24 My contribution has been to negotiate the contracts, design the courses
25 and
26 interactive exercises, and lead the programmes through which we try to
27 help
28 people develop both competence and confidence in their own abilities.
29 Every
30 course is a negotiation between the presenters and the participants.

31 I am now largely retired. My observations below thus are those of an
32 interested observer, viewing our profession from the sidelines.

33 **2. Systemic Shifts**

34 *Europe is facing profound political, economic, and social transformations—*
35 *fragmented power structures, regional conflicts, climate pressures,*
36 *migration. In your area, which of these shifts has the greatest impact on*
37 *negotiation today, and why?*

38 *(Optional): What are the biggest challenges in the way we negotiate these*
issues currently?

39 I don't think it possible to differentiate between these transformations.
40 The essence of our time is multi-dimensional inter-penetrated
41 transformation, a cacophony of complex change at ever-increasing pace.

..3.1.1. Challenges

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The challenge in any negotiation now is to discern how this *mix* of factors is impacting *precisely* on the issues and actors in the negotiation.

..1.1. Geopolitical

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Structurally, the principal current challenge for Europe is adjusting to the disengagement of the United States from its traditional allegiances, and the wider disruption of the post-World War II global order. These seismic shifts also offer opportunities for European states and institutions to forge more cohesive negotiating positions.

..1.2. Social

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More fundamentally, the biggest challenge to us all is the loss of the anchor of truth, a casualty of exponential growth in the capacities and manipulability of information technology.

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3. Most Demanding Negotiation You Have Participated in / Observed Recently

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What made it demanding, and what were central variables in reaching (or not

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reaching)

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agreement?

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Like the rest of the world, I have observed with dismay the failed

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negotiations between Russia and Ukraine, and the Government of Israel and

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Hamas, respectively, in which one or both of the parties is using the

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negotiating process as a tool in the conflict. The moment of 'ripeness' has

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not yet been reached.

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4. Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration

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The conference aims to bridge researchers, practitioners, and civil society.

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Where do you see the biggest gap between academic insight and practice, and how might we close it?

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(Optional): How could civil society actors and/or citizens be included to

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close the gap?

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This conference is encouraging evidence that the gap is already closing.

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When I began forty years ago many academics looked down as from Olympus on

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practitioners, who for their part often disregarded the relevance of

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academic research, in a relationship of mutual incomprehension. Gradually,

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the humility required of successful negotiation has grown on both sides.

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Cross-disciplinary conferences such as this, crucially including the

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voice(s) of civil society and the young, will serve as incubators and

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multipliers of more grown-up collaboration.

..4.3. Bridging Strategy

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5. European Distinctiveness

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Do you think negotiation in Europe differs in any systematic way from other regions? Give an example.

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(If yes): What could we learn from other negotiation cultures?

76 All negotiation is a function of the culture or cultures of the
77 participants. The ASEAN Way, the EU exemplify specific frames of
reference.
78 Each offers lessons others can learn with advantage, for example about
79 managing power differential. I wish closer attention were paid to the
80 wisdoms of indigenous tribal conflict resolution.

81 The EU *acquis communautaire* is to me the most advanced form of
governance
82 yet devised, with its intricate combination of federal and
83 inter-governmental competencies, and treaty-based balance of institutional
84 powers. Its decision-making can be cumbersome and slow, but 'permanent
85 negotiation' grinds inexorably to agreement among highly disparate actors.

..2.1. European

86 The EU system of negotiation, however, rests on the foundations of liberal
87 democracy – the Monnet model, challenged now by the rise in Europe of
88 populist authoritarianism as a legitimate alternative form of governance.
89 Encouragingly, the suddenness and urgency of the challenge appears to
90 have jolted EU senior decision-makers into more rapid than usual response.

..2.1. European

..2.1. European

..5.1. Essential Skills a

91 In the end, though, the essence of successful negotiation is universal –
92 active listening.

93 6. Key Skill for Tomorrow's Negotiators

94 *If you could add one new competency to every European negotiator's*
toolkit,
95 *what would it be?*
96 *What would you recommend to teach those skills to the next generation of*
97 *negotiators?*

..5.1. Essential Skills a

98 The key to effective negotiation is not a skill but a quality – *emotional*
99 *intelligence* – the capacity to examine honestly the strengths and
100 weaknesses of your own position, and to imagine empathetically being the
101 other: why are they at the table, what do they want, what do they fear?
102 Understanding and accepting the validity of the needs of the other(s)
103 requires *humility*, often difficult for the more powerful forced to
104 compromise.

..5.1. Essential Skills a

..5.3. Teaching Method

105 Both of these qualities, innate in humans though more deeply buried in
106 some
107 than in others, can be *encouraged*. Active listening is a skill that can be
108 taught, by example and by interactive exercises of simulation and role-play.
109 The scholar or practitioner serves not so much as authority of knowledge
as mentor/facilitator drawing out the capacities of the learner.

110 **7. Research or Practice Question Still Unanswered**
111 *What is the one negotiation question you wish scholars or practitioners*
112 *would tackle next?*

..6.1. Research Questic [113 I wish more attention were paid to the psychology of conflict. The
114 substantive realities are well-understood; conflict is endemic in human
115 behaviour. Strategies of conflict resolution are much studied and practised.
..6.1. Research Questic [116 But what is it in the mind and lived-experience of the parties that are at
117 the root of the particular conflict? I would focus on 'Getting to *Why?*'.

118 **8. Book and Film**
119 *If you had to recommend one book and one film on negotiation, what would*
120 *they be?*

121 Book: Bessel van der Kolk, *The Body Keeps the Score*, on the impact of
122 trauma on consciousness and conflict; (followed by Sun Tse, *The Art of*
123 *War*,
on the psychology of strategy and tactics)

124 Film: Robert Cooper, *The Agreement*, a remarkable behind the scenes
125 chronicle of overcoming obstacles; (followed by Alex Garland, *Civil War*
126 (2024), as a reminder of the consequence of failure to agree)